

Simulated Star Fields in Dense Regions

L. Lindegren (30 January 1998)

SAG_LL_013

1 Introduction

This note gives an example of how some of the densest parts of the sky may look like for the GAIA main field detector. Realistic star counts in the I band were used to generate a star field, which was then converted to expected photon counts per pixel using current estimates for the photometric response, PSF, pixel size and integration time. Noise was not added, however, since that would mask many of the effects that the example is intended to illustrate.

2 Star counts in some dense regions

In the following N is the cumulative density of stars in a given region, expressed as the number of stars per square degree brighter than magnitude I .

The star count model in SAG_LL_012 has its maximum density N_0 in the direction towards the galactic centre, $l = b = 0$. However, the model is not expected to be reliable at small galactic latitudes and needs to be complemented with actual star counts. At or around the detection limit of GAIA ($I \simeq 20$) the highest star densities are expected in globular clusters, in some low-extinction areas near the galactic plane such as Baade's Window, and in the central region of the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC). Globular clusters are not considered here, due to their complex structure.

In Baade's Window ($l \simeq +1^\circ$, $b \simeq -4^\circ$) star counts were derived from the OGLE colour-magnitude diagram as reported in Paczynski et al. (AJ 107, 2060, 1994), using V and $V-I$ data available by anonymous ftp. These are reasonably complete to $I \simeq 18.5$ and completeness corrections could be applied down to $I \simeq 20$. For fainter magnitudes the counts were extrapolated assuming a constant $d \lg N/dI \simeq 0.5$, as observed between $I = 18$ and 20. This is probably a pessimistic extrapolation, as judged both from a galaxy model without extinction (where the counts saturate for $I > 25$) and from HST counts in smaller areas down to $I \simeq 22$ (Holtzman et al., AJ 106, 1826, 1993).

Data for the LMC Bar were taken from HST/PC observations on the y and b scales of the $uvby$ system (Ardeberg et al., A&A 322, L13, 1997). The approximate transformation $I = y - 1.63(b - y)$ was used to derive N by direct counting down to $I \simeq 22$. A nearly constant $d \lg N/dI \simeq 0.39$ was found, and this was then used to extrapolate to fainter magnitudes.

Results from the galaxy model (N_0), for Baade's Window (N_{BW}) and the LMC Bar (N_{LMC}) are compared in Table 1. The highest densities are found in Baade's Window, and those counts were therefore used in the subsequent simulation.

Table 1. Comparison of star counts (N = number of stars per square degree brighter than magnitude I) in some dense regions. N_0 : towards the galactic centre according to SAG.LL.012; N_{BW} : in Baade’s Window; N_{LMC} : in the centre of the LMC Bar.

I	$\lg N_0$	$\lg N_{\text{BW}}$	$\lg N_{\text{LMC}}$
15.0	4.06	4.67	4.0
16.0	4.38	5.08	4.7
17.0	4.67	5.29	4.9
18.0	4.99	5.50	5.3
19.0	5.34	5.98	5.77
20.0	5.73	6.45	6.13
21.0	6.06	6.93	6.54
22.0	6.31	7.40	6.90
23.0	6.53	7.88	7.29
24.0	6.72	8.36	7.68
25.0	6.91	8.83	8.07

3 Simulated star field

Figure 1 shows a field of 10×10 arcsec² simulated with the density function N_{BW} according to Table 1. The magnitudes were drawn from a continuous distribution obtained by linear interpolation in the $I/\lg N$ table over the interval $15 \leq I \leq 25$. The x and y positions were drawn from independent uniform distributions. The simulation gave a total of 5347 stars in the field (the expected number was 5217). The brightest star in the field is $I \simeq 15.1$. Figure 2 shows the stars with $I < 20.5$, approximately the expected detection limit for GAIA.

4 Simulated detector response

Given the list of star positions and magnitudes, the detector response was generated with the following assumptions, based on the payload design presented at the MMS mid-term review in January 1998:

- the photoelectron rate for $I = 20$ was set to 175 Hz (corresponding to a K3III star);
- the integration time was 1 s;
- the optical PSF was taken to be a gaussian with $\sigma_x = 0.037$ arcsec and $\sigma_y = 0.087$ arcsec;
- the pixel size was $9 \mu\text{m}$ in the scanning direction (x) and $30 \mu\text{m}$ in the transverse direction (y);
- the focal length was 50 m.

For each star the PSF was evaluated at 32 points in each pixel and added to the corresponding pixel value after proper weighting to take into account the TDI smearing. No background, readout or photon noise was added. The pixel values discussed below are thus strictly proportional to the stellar photon fluxes smeared by the PSF, pixel geometry, and TDI. They are expressed in electrons per pixel.

Figure 3 shows a map of the pixel values for the lower-left corner of the field (approximately 2×2 arcsec²). The brightest star in the subfield ($I \simeq 19.3$) stands out with a peak of about 52 e, while the many fainter stars blend into an irregular background. Figure 4 is a histogram of all the pixel values in the 10×10 arcsec² field.

Figures 5 to 10 show which pixels exceed a given threshold: 100, 40, 25, 16, 10 and 7 electrons. Given a certain rms fluctuation due to the readout noise and photon noise of the background (say 15 electrons), these maps give an impression of what could reasonably be detected in such a field, using a simple threshold criterion, and the degree of image crowding at that level.

It appears that a detection limit around $I = 20$ could be achieved, without significant problems due to crowding or (stellar) background non-uniformity, even in this field of rather extreme density.

Figure 1. A simulated star field of 10×10 arcsec² in Baade's Window. 5347 stars in the magnitude range $I = 15.$ to 25.0 are shown.

Figure 2. Same as Figure 1 but showing only the stars brighter than $I = 20.5.$

Figure 3. The lower-left part (2×2 arcsec²) of the simulated field in Figure 1, after convolution with the GAIA PFS and TDI smearing, and conversion to expected number of electrons per pixel. The coordinates are pixel numbers along (x) and perpendicular to the scanning (y). No background, readout or photon noise was added.

Figure 4. Histogram of pixel values (in electrons) for the whole 10×10 arcsec² field.

Figure 5. Map of pixel values exceeding 100 electrons ($I_{\max} \simeq 18.5$), shown as black rectangles. Pixel corners are marked with a dot.

Figure 6. Map of pixel values exceeding 40 electrons ($I_{\max} \simeq 19.5$).

Figure 7. Map of pixel values exceeding 25 electrons ($I_{\max} \simeq 20.0$).

Figure 8. Map of pixel values exceeding 16 electrons ($I_{\max} \simeq 20.5$).

Figure 9. Map of pixel values exceeding 10 electrons ($I_{\max} \simeq 21.0$).

Figure 10. Map of pixel values exceeding 7 electrons ($I_{\max} \simeq 21.4$).